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The Impact of Brand Concept Dimensions on Customer Commitment (A survey of Apple iPhone Users in Bandung, Indonesia)

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Abstract: *Technology needs, especially smartphones, are now very huge; it cannot be denied that many smartphone brands compete with each other to get the highest market share. Overall, several well-known brands such as Samsung, Xiaomi and Oppo are the top three smartphone brands that are most widely used in Indonesia, but there is one smartphone that, although it has a market share not as big as the three brands, is considered the most exclusive because the market is only for a certain group of people who understands the brand, the Apple iPhone. The purpose of this research is to find out whether the brand concept possessed by the Apple iPhone can impact customer commitment, because it is known that the Apple iPhone users tend to continue to use the same iPhone brand, despite other competing brands in the same product category. The research method used is the descriptive research method with a quantitative approach, whereby the population is the Apple iPhone users in the city of Bandung. Data collection is by questionnaires, interviews and observations, while the data analysis technique uses descriptive analysis and also multiple linear regression analysis. The results showed that brand concept dimensions consisting of aesthetic benefits, functional benefits and symbolic benefits had a significant influence in shaping customer commitment. As for the three dimensions of the brand concept, it is known that symbolic benefits have the strongest impact on customer commitment compared to the other two dimensions.*

Keywords: *Brand Concept Dimension, Customer Commitment, Apple iPhone*

Background

In the process of globalization, it is inseparable from change, these changes also impact business competition, which requires companies to behave and act quickly, in order to face competition in a business environment that moves very dynamic and full of uncertainty. Therefore, every company is required to compete competitively to create and maintain customer commitment. At present a company's competition to attract the attention of customers has not focused on functional products such as product use, but nowadays products are strongly associated with brands that can provide their own value for their use, it is now known that the role of brands has shifted. At a low level of competition a brand only

distinguishes between products and other products or in other words, a brand is just a name. In contrast, at the high level of competition that makes a brand an identity of a product, the more time it develops, the company begins to realize the importance of a brand to a company, because it is a high-value asset. Competition in the mobile phone industry is very tight, encouraging smartphone product manufacturers to continue to grow to compete with market share.

According to preliminary data from the International Data Corporation (IDC) Worldwide Quarterly Mobile Phone Tracker, smartphone vendors shipped a total of 355.2 million units during the third quarter of 2018 (3Q18), resulting in a year-over-year decline of 6.0%. This was the fourth consecutive quarter of year-over-year declines for the global smartphone market, which raises questions about the market's future. IDC maintains its view that the market will return to growth in 2019, but at this stage it is too early to tell what that growth will look like.

Figure 1. IDC Quarterly Mobile Phone Tracker, November 1, 2018
Source: IDC.com

Steve Jobs, described Apple as a "mobile devices company" - the largest one in the world. Apple is making many services and functionality which consumers use accessible on whatever (Apple) device they happen to be using at the time, be it on their desk, lap, fingertips or wrist.

For years now Apple iPhone products have been in the leading pack in sales worldwide, the statistics (see table in **figure 1.1** above) shows that Apple iPhone products were among the top 4 most sold products in the world. The most powerful products for business are the ones people already love to use. Apple products have always been designed

for the way we work as much as for the way we live (Appleinc.com). Some of the other mobile phone companies are much more technically oriented than customer oriented, which has a sizable effect on how they prioritize, according to “Ira Kalb”, clinical marketing professor at the USC Marshall School of Business.

Figure 2. Number of Indonesian Smartphone Users in 2013-2018

Source: repository.unpas.ac.id

As seen in figure 2 above, the number of smartphone users in Indonesia from 2013-2018 continued to increase. In 2013 the number of smartphone users in Indonesia only reached 27.4 million people. However, there was a sharp increase of 10.9 million in 2014 which was 39.78% when compared to 2013. Even so, in the following years, the percentage increase in the number of smartphone users in Indonesia gradually declined, with 32.95% in 2016, 24.78% in 2017 and 18.93% in 2018. However, despite a decrease in percentage increase, the number of smartphone users in Indonesia remained increased. In addition, growing markets like India and Indonesia, where Samsung has held leading positions for many years, are being changed by the rapid growth of Chinese brands like Xiaomi, OPPO, and vivo. Also, the International Data Corporation’s (IDC's) Quarterly Mobile Phone Tracker, stated that the smartphone shipments in Indonesia reached 9.4 million units in 2Q18, a growth of 22% quarter over quarter (QoQ) and 18% over the same period last year, marking the highest shipments ever recorded in Indonesia.

Figure 3. IDC Top-5 Vendor Smartphone Indonesia-Q318

Source: Selular.ID

Apple expanded their Research and Development (R & D) reach into the Asian region. Apple chose Indonesia as the headquarters of their research and innovation (Bella; 2018).

Bandung can be referred to as a city in Indonesia that never stops giving birth to creative and innovative ideas. Most of the current trends start from the city of Bandung. The main actors who play an important role in the birth of these creative ideas are young people who seem to continue to thirst for inspiration in all fields, to maintain the existence of the city as the center of the creative industry not only at the local level of Indonesia, but also as the main barometer of creativity for Asian youths, Southeast Asia even more broadly. The creativity of young people in the city of Bandung continues to grow, certainly not apart from the role of information and communication technology used. The form of information and communication technology that is often used by young entrepreneurs in Bandung, one of which is a smartphone with various types and brands. (Firdaus; 2013).

The city of Bandung is the largest in the province of West Java, and the population of the province of West Java is the largest in Indonesia compared to other provinces in Indonesia. Based on population, the highest number of internet users is in West Java as many as 16.4 million, one of which is in Bandung with cell phone usage reaching 92% spread in Java & Bali. Bandung is also known as one of the most technologically aware cities and has a young generation that is almost entirely aware of innovating technology; even Bandung itself

strongly supports the advancement of technology through its government (Rachmani, 2015). For some people, the use of smartphones is not just a tool to communicate like an ordinary mobile phone, but can be used as a tool to work using software provided by software developers.

In Indonesia, it is one of the targets of Chinese smartphone companies to expand its market. The city of Bandung is one of the potential market targets for Chinese smartphones. The city of Bandung in 2015 was chosen, as the world's top 6 finalists for Smart City innovation from the World Smart City Organization in Barcelona representing Indonesia. The city of Bandung got the nickname, because its people actively helped the city's development using smartphones. This means that people in the city of Bandung have quite a lot of smartphone users and also means having a high purchasing power for smartphones. That way it can benefit Chinese smartphone manufacturers to market their products (Ramadhan&Yulianna, 2016).

However, a separate phenomenon is that the Apple iPhone market share in Indonesia is still inferior to other brands. In the figure 3 above, it is explained that the Apple iPhone market share falls in the category (written as *others* with 13%), this signifies that Apple iPhone isn't among the top five smartphone brands in Indonesia in regards to unit market share, with the new Chinese brands displacing Apple iPhone in the leading position. What's interesting is that Apple only sells far fewer product variants than its competitors in Bandung Indonesia, only one to two variants of cellphone products per year and all of them are products that are in the upper class and niche market, while these other upcoming Chinese brands such as Xiaomi, Oppo, Vivo etc offer different variants of smartphone products for various segmentations ranging from the lower class to the middle class, at a lower rate compared to the Apple iPhones, yet these factors doesn't discourage the Apple iPhone users/customers (Venta, Lestari and Pamungkas; 2016).

So, what makes Apple iPhone brand generate such commitment among its customers, especially in Bandung Indonesia?

In developing a strategic marketing plan for a company, brand serves as a guide to understanding the purpose of the key business objectives. It enables the company to align a marketing plan with those objectives and fulfill the overarching strategy. Companies will always be at the risk of decreased sales or not gaining any sales at all if the role of brand is not well maintained. Different things can impact a brand of a company or its product and thus the sales. Therefore, a company must be assertive on how their brand is portrayed to consumers. The brand of a company sends its customers through its message and hence it

tells the story of what the company is and how it operates. There are certain factors that can limit the sales of a product that the company cannot control-be it natural disaster, price increase of raw materials or something else-however the goal is always to sell products. This is not always possible if the price increases, because though a consumer is aware of it and is a repeat purchaser of a certain brand, he /she might not prefer it, if the price increases beyond his/her capacity (Pinson &Brosdahl, 2014).

Problem Identification

Based on the description of the background of the research above, the problems in this study can be identified as follows:

1. How is the customers' response of Brand Concept dimensions of Apple iPhone?
2. How is the Customer Commitment of Apple iPhone?
3. What is the Simultaneous impact of Brand Concept dimensions (Aesthetic, Functional and Symbolic benefits) on Customer Commitment?
4. What is the Partial impact of Brand Concept dimensions (Aesthetic, Functional and Symbolic benefits) on Customer Commitment?

Research Objectives

The objectives of this study are:

1. To analyze the customers' response of Brand Concept dimensions of Apple iPhone.
2. To analyze the Customer Commitment of Apple iPhone
3. To analyze the Simultaneous impact of Brand Concept dimensions (Aesthetic, Functional and Symbolic benefits) on Customer Commitment
4. To analyze the Partial impact of Brand Concept dimensions (Aesthetic, Functional and Symbolic benefits) on Customer Commitment

Literature Review

Dimensions of Brand Concept

There are three broad categories of brand concepts, defined in accordance with basic consumer needs: *Aesthetic, Functional and Symbolic* (Park et al, 1986).

1. Aesthetic Benefits

The Aesthetic benefits which is also known as Experiential benefits are designed to fulfill consumer's needs for sensory pleasure (Jeon and Lee, 2016). "*Aesthetics*" comes from the Greek word aesthesis, referring to sensory perception and understanding (Krishna et al., 2010; Kumar and Garg, 2010). In the eighteenth century, the philosopher Baumgarten picked up the term and changed its meaning into gratification of the senses delight (Goldman, 2001). Brands with an experiential concept primarily serve as fulfilling needs of sensory pleasure, variety or cognitive stimulation. Aesthetics is a powerful source for the impressions and reactions that costumers have about a brand. A very well consolidated identity based on aesthetics must represent the starting point of any effort aimed to gain and retain the clients.

The term "aesthetics in marketing" refers to promoting sensory experiences related to products, designed to contribute to the brand's organization or identity.

The aesthetics in marketing, compared to other areas, refers to structural and referential qualities of the aesthetics of an organization or brand that are working together. While some of consumers' perceptions are direct, others are cognitively mediated. Satisfaction may be given both by the inherent qualities and structural features of the product and by the meanings conveyed by the aesthetic image of an organization or a brand.

Nowadays, the role that the aesthetics plays in a firm is that of a main element of differentiation regardless of the activity filed from which the firm derives from. Moreover, the success of many companies in competitive markets is not due only because of the high quality products or services, but also of using the aesthetics.

Aesthetic experiences are becoming increasingly relevant to the marketing due to growing importance of experiential aspects of consumption (Hirschman and Holbrook, 1982). Aesthetic appeal and design have been of interest to human beings and have captured their imagination throughout history (Patrick and Hagtvedt, 2011; Krishna et al., 2010).

Aesthetic experiences can have a deep-rooted influence on consumer affect, cognition and behavior. In a marketing context, aesthetic needs are defined as desires for products that provide aesthetic pleasure. When consumers take product quality for granted, aesthetics becomes an important criterion (Park et al., 1986; Park et al., 2013) in the purchasing decision. Aesthetics have been investigated in the visual sense, but other senses, for example, taste, smell and the interaction of senses, do constitute aesthetic experiences in traditional

marketing research (Krishna et al., 2010). The full form of appreciation of an aesthetic experience comes from the combination of sensory input (Kumar and Garg, 2010).

2. Functional Benefits

The Functional benefits should emphasize the functional performance. Prior research has defined functional value as the ability to perform functions in the everyday life of a consumer (Hirschman and Holbrook, 1982). Functional needs are defined as those that motivate the search for products that solve consumption-related problems (Park et al., 1986; Park et al., 2013).

These needs are linked to basic motivations and are met by products with functional performance. Therefore, a functional brand is designed to solve externally generated consumption needs (Chaudhuri and Holbrook, 2001; Brakus et al., 2009). Park et al. (2010) indicate that brands can be managed to reduce uncertainty in consumers' lives and enable the attainment of desired outcomes by facilitating control and efficacy. Hence, functional brands are related to product performance. Brands with visual representations of functional benefits are capable of reminding customers of the brand's functionality and/or communicating such benefits to them (Keller, 1993). In simple terms, a brand with a functional concept is defined as one designed to solve externally generated consumption needs (e.g. solve a problem, resolve a conflict etc.).

3. Symbolic Benefits

The Symbolic benefits should emphasize the relationship between brand and self-identification. These brands can reflect a part of consumer's identities. Park et al. (2013) defined self-expressiveness brand as the brand with symbolic concept. Brands have the ability to help express or define customers' actual or desired selves and to differentiate customers' selves from those of others (McCracken, 1990). Brands also become relevant to customers by connecting the individual to others who share similar values and beliefs. Symbolic brand concepts pertain to products and brands that fulfill internally generated needs for self-enhancement, group membership or ego-identification.

Symbolic needs are defined as desires for products that fulfill internally generated needs for self-enhancement, social role or ego-identification (Holbrook and Hirschman, 1982). A symbolic brand benefit is one that is designed to associate the individual with a desired group, role or self-image (Park et al., 1986). Customers may value the prestige,

exclusivity or fashionability of a brand because it relates positively to their self-concept. A symbolic brand can be a critical tool for conveying associations between the brand and the self, which in turn helps the consumer see the brand as part of them (Hirschman and Holbrook, 1982). Brands with symbolic benefits have the potential to not only express brand-self associations but also to reinforce and strengthen them, thus enhancing customers' willingness to exert effort and invest resources towards sustaining their relationship with the brand (McCracken, 1990; Park et al., 2010)

Customer Commitment

Commitment can be a source of sustainable competitive advantage to a firm because it offers cost reduction, enhanced profits, positive word-of-mouth and the prospect of sales at a premium price (Hur et al., 2010). As a result of the nature of mobile phones companies, customers are more susceptible to exhibit commitment behavior towards brands that come closest to meeting their expectations. Additionally, the emotional sense of fulfillment that customers feel when they perceive high-quality services can elicit an emotional support for the brand and cause them to not only exhibit repurchase behavior, but also engage in positive word-of-mouth.

For the purposes of the present study, three types of commitment are proposed: (1) affective commitment; (2) calculative commitment; and (3) normative commitment (Bansal, Irving, & Taylor, 2004; Gustafsson et al., 2005). Drawing on the definitions and classifications used in previous studies, these three categories of commitment can be summarized as follows:

1. Affective commitment

According to Fullerton (2003), Affective commitment is the emotional type of commitment; this is the customer's emotional attachment to the brand. As proffered previously, consumers often exhibit strong feelings about protecting and maintaining their health. It is proposed that this emotional disposition is tied to brand commitment. It simply reflects the extent to which a customer identifies with and feels a sense of positive attachment to a brand. It is the predisposition to continue stable transactions over the long term by utilizing social bonds and familiar relations with a firm (Geyskens et al., 1996). Such emotional ties are often closely connected to brand image and/ or customer's lifestyle.

Affective commitment relates to the psychological attachment where a self-brand connection is created (Hsiao et al., 2015; Kemp et al., 2014). It is the emotional

attachment of the customer to the brand, based on his or her identification with it (Evanschitzky et al., 2006). Affective commitment reflects the customer's desire to maintain the relationship (Jones et al., 2010). The pillars of affective commitment are shared values, identification, and attachment (Fullerton, 2005; Gruen et al., 2000). This emotional link has positive consequences on customer behaviour, such as retention, brand repurchase, positive word of mouth and willingness to pay a price premium (Albert and Merunka, 2013). Customers who are affectively committed to a brand are less vulnerable to switch to alternative brands and are less expensive to retain (Kemp et al., 2014). Affectively committed customers' relationship with the brand is broader because psychological emotions control the functional and economic factors, and deeper, because the customers identify themselves with the brand and become less sensitive to price or convenience (Mason and Simmons, 2012).

2. Calculative/Continuance commitment

Continuance commitment, in contrast, is the type of commitment that is more utilitarian in nature; it involves the intent to continue a relationship because of calculative costs and scarcity alternatives. It reflects the sense of bonding resulting from perceived high switching costs, lack of viable alternatives or a cognitive evaluation of the costs inherent with defecting a brand (Davis-Sramek et al., 2009; Gustafsson et al., 2005; Fullerton, 2003; Geyskens et al., 1996). Also known as calculative commitment, continuance commitment comprises a more negative, psychologically based motivation that is appropriately distinct from affective commitment (Sweeney and Swait, 2008; Geyskens et al., 1996). Financial considerations (such as searching costs and switching cost) play a significant role in this type of commitment (Anderson & Weitz, 1992; Geyskens et al., 1996).

Continuance or calculative commitment represents a more rational, economic-based dependence on a product or brand, founded in the consumer's perception of no other attractive alternatives or too high switching costs, that make difficult to end the relationship (Evanschitzky et al., 2006; Fullerton, 2005).

3. Normative commitment

Normative commitment refers to a sense of obligation (Bansal et al., 2004). The concept of 'normative commitment' was originally developed in the context of workplace commitment (Meyer & Allen, 1997), but it has application in services

marketing when consumers feel that it is the ‘right thing to do’ to remain with a given service provider. Normative commitment develops through socialization as individuals internalize a set of norms concerning appropriate behaviour (such as the acceptability or non-acceptability of switching service providers) (Bansal et al., 2004).

Research Hypothesis

Based on the background of the problem and the framework above described in the research model, the following research hypothesis is formulated.

- H1: Brand Concept Dimensions simultaneously impacts customer commitment.
- H2: Aesthetic benefit partially impacts customer commitment
- H3: Functional benefit partially impacts customer commitment
- H4: Symbolic benefit partially impacts customer commitment

Research Model

Research Design

Research design or method is defined as the blue print for the research process. It shows exactly how the study will be conducted in technical terms. However, it elaborates how the researcher will carry out sample selection, the data collection instruments that were used and research procedures among other specific tasks. The research method used is the descriptive research method with a quantitative approach. Quantitative approaches, carried out to examine certain population or sample, using statistical analysis aims to test the research hypothesis in the form of a causal relationship, i.e. causal relationship between independent variables (which is affect) and the dependent variable (which is influenced), (Sugiyono, 2018).

Population

Population is defined as the total collection of elements to be studied (Cooper & Schindler, 2014), so my research population is the population of the Apple iPhone users in Bandung. A sample is the unit from which data on the investigated matter is extracted with a purpose of drawing analysis, conclusions and generalization (Cooper & Schindler, 2014). The study will neither be based on a specific age group nor the gender, rather it will based on the Apple iPhone users living in Bandung.

Sampling Technique

The study will use the probability sampling design where a purposive sampling technique will be adopted. Purposive sampling (also known as judgment, selective or subjective sampling) is a sampling technique in which researcher relies on his or her own judgment when choosing members of population to participate in the study. According to John Dudovskiy (2018); Purposive sampling is a non-probability sampling method and it occurs when elements selected for the sample are chosen by the judgment of the researcher.

The criteria behind selecting a purposive sampling technique among other probability sampling techniques is because the study will focus on specific group of the general population, since the researcher wants to gain insight about Apple iPhone brand users in Bandung. The respondents' prerequisites for this purposive sampling technique are:

- Customers who have been using the Apple iPhone for a minimum of two years.

This is more relevant to my study to determine the customer commitment of Apple iPhone users in a long term scale. In a marketing context, customers with commitment intend to continue a long-term relationship and have a willingness to remain in the relationship (Chaudhuri and Holbrook, 2001; Oliver, 1999) in the journal by Joo-Eon Jeon,(2017).

Results and Discussion

After knowing descriptively from the results of data collection through a questionnaire, the next step is to do multiple regression analysis with the aim to answer the hypotheses presented in the previous chapter.

Simultaneous Test Results (Test F)

The first hypothesis to be tested is the simultaneous hypothesis, namely the impact of brand concept dimensions simultaneously on customer commitment using the ANOVA test.

The statistical hypothesis is as follows:

H_0 : there is no impact of the brand concept dimensions simultaneously on customer commitment.

H_a : there is an impact of the brand concept dimensions simultaneously on customer commitment.

While the results of statistical calculations are:

Table 1 Simultaneous Test Using ANOVA

ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2165.012	3	721.671	36.935	.000 ^a
	Residual	1875.748	96	19.539		
	Total	4040.760	99			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Aesthetic benefits, Functional Benefits, Symbolic benefits

b. Dependent Variable: Customer Commitment

The simultaneous test results using the ANOVA test in table 4.12 show a significance value (sig) of 0.000 which is smaller than the alpha value (0.05), besides, it can also be seen that the value of F_{count} (36.935) is greater than the F_{table} (2.31) for 100 respondents, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, so based on the simultaneous hypothesis proposed above, it can be said that simultaneously, the brand concept dimensions (Aesthetic, Functional and Symbolic benefits) has an impact on customer commitment (Y).

Once a concept is selected for a brand, Park et al. (1986) advised that the concept, for the sake of consistency, should be maintained throughout the brand's life. This latter point

has not been without controversy and, e.g. McEnally and Chernatony (1999) question the premise whether brands always should stick to their initial concept, even when consumer preferences and other external variables may change. By the same token, Bhat and Reddy (1998) voice their concern of whether brands always should be perceived as being either functional or symbolic, so that in the end in can brings out the customer's commitment for their product

Calculation Results of the Determination Coefficient

Then to find out how much influence the X variables simultaneously has on the Y variable, the writer uses the coefficient of determination formula, which results can be seen in table 2 below:

Table 2 Coefficient of Determination Test

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.732 ^a	.536	.521	4.42030

a. Predictors: (Constant), Aesthetic benefits, Functional Benefits, Symbolic benefits

In table 2 it is shown the Adjusted Rsquare value of 0.521 so that the value of the Coefficient of Determination (CD) can be calculated which is $0.521 \times 100\% = 52.1\%$ which indicates that the brand concept dimensions simultaneously has an impact of 52.1% in forming customer commitment, the remaining 47.9% is influenced by other variables. The value used is the adjusted R^2 to evaluate the regression model, because the value can go up and down based on significance of independent variables, (Ghozali, 2009).

T-Test Results

T test is a partial test of the regression coefficient between the independent variables on the dependent variable. The acceptance criteria for partial hypotheses is done by comparing the value of t count with t_{table} , which if $t_{count} > t_{table}$ then H_0 is rejected, and vice versa. The results of the t test can be seen in the table below:

Table 3 Partial Test Results

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	4.229	2.839		1.489	.140
	Aesthetics benefit	.577	.212	.459	2.723	.008
	Functional Benefit	.706	.275	.445	2.568	.012
	Symbolic benefit	.955	.274	.535	3.493	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Commitment

Table 3 above shows that the r value is 0.459 and the significance value (sig) of Aesthetic benefits variable on Customer commitment is 0.008, which is smaller than alpha value (0.05), besides, it is also known that the value of tcount is 2.723 which is greater than t-table (1.984), then Ho2 is rejected and Ha2 is accepted, so based on the hypothesis criteria (2) proposed above, it can be said that the Aesthetic benefits (X1) have an impact on the Customer commitment (Y).

Previous research conducted by Jeon (2017) revealed that Aesthetic benefits are indeed one of the dimensions in a brand concept that can impact Customer commitment. Aesthetic experiences can have a deep-rooted influence on consumer effect, cognition and behavior. In a marketing context, aesthetic needs are defined as products for products that provide aesthetic pleasure. When consumers take quality products for granted, aesthetics becomes an important criterion (Park et al., 1986; Park et al., 2013) in the purchasing decision. The better the aesthetics that a product has, the more consumers will have a greater commitment to the brand.

Likewise, based on the results of interviews with several respondents, it is known that the iPhone continues to increase in terms of design. Whereby, the latest design is the iPhone X series, which has the most futuristic design and no longer has a home button, so it is said to be one of the pioneers of smartphone design like this. If a smartphone does not change in its design, then of course consumers will be able to easily switch to other brands that are considered to have better designs.

Besides that, it can also be seen in table 3 above, that the the r value is 0.445 and the significance value (sig) of Functional benefits variable towards Customer commitment is 0.012, which is smaller than alpha value (0.05), besides, it is also known that the tcount is 2.568 which is greater than ttable (1.984), then Ho3 is rejected and Ha3 is accepted, so based on the hypothesis criteria (3) proposed above, it can be said that the Functional benefits (X2) have an impact on the Customer commitment (Y).

The Functional benefits should emphasize the functional performance. Prior research has defined functional value as the ability to perform functions in the everyday life of a consumer (Hirschman and Holbrook, 1982). Functional needs are defined as those that motivate the search for products that solve consumption-related problems (Park et al., 1986; Park et al., 2013). These needs are linked to basic motivations and are met by products with functional performance. The results of research by Jeon (2017) prove that when a brand has a practical function and is easy to operate, consumers also tend to prefer smartphones like that.

Likewise, the results of research conducted by Joseph (2011) describe that consumers can increase their commitment and loyalty in using a brand if the brand does offer a different function and is more useful than other brands. Brands with visual representations of functional benefits are capable of reminding customers of the brand's functionality and/or communicating such benefits to them (Keller, 1993).

Table 3 also shows that the r value is 0.535 and the significance value (sig) of the Symbolic benefits variable on Customer commitment is 0.001, which is smaller than the alpha value (0.05), besides, it is also known that the value of tcount is 3.493 which is greater than ttable (1.984), then Ho4 is rejected and Ha4 is accepted, so based on the hypothesis criteria (4) proposed above, it can be said that the Symbolic benefits (X3) have an impact on the Customer commitment (Y).

Jeon (2017) proved in his research that brands are often just a symbol for a user, what is meant by a symbol here is when the brand's users feel proud and feel exclusive when using a brand. The same was said by several respondents interviewed, where they felt exclusive and also different from others when they held the iPhone in his hand.

4.5.4 Regression Model Result

After knowing the results of the simultaneous test using ANOVA, as well as the results of the partial test using t-test, the next step is analyzing the regression model formed from the results of this study. The results of testing the regression model can be seen in the table 4.13, the regression equation for this study is obtained as follows:

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \beta_3 x_3 + \varepsilon$$

$$Y = 4.229 + 0.577X1 + 0.706X2 + 0.955X3 + \varepsilon$$

The following is an explanation of the results of the regression equation above:

- Constant (a) = 4.229, that if the three dimensions of Brand concept rises in one unit, the Customer Commitment variable will increase (fulfilled) by 4.229 units
- The Aesthetic benefits regression coefficient (b1) = 0.577, the dimension of Aesthetic benefits increases by 1 unit, the Customer commitment will increase by 0.577 assuming the other variables are constant.
- The Functional benefits regression coefficient (b2) = 0.706, the dimension of the Functional benefits rises by 1 unit, the Customer commitment will increase by 0.706 assuming the other variables are constant.
- The Symbolic benefits regression coefficient (b3) = 0.955, the Symbolic benefit dimension rises by 1 unit, the Customer commitment will increase by 0.955 assuming the other variables are constant.

Furthermore, when viewed from each regression coefficient it turns out that the most influential is the Symbolic benefits; this shows that Symbolic benefits turns out to be the most dominant dimension to the Customer commitment of the Apple iPhone users..

Conclusion

Based on the results of the research presented in the previous chapter, this study can be concluded as follows:

1. Based on customer assessment in this research showed that aesthetic benefit, functional benefit and symbolic benefit which are the dimensions of brand concept overall exist in good category.

Total average score of aesthetic benefits is 4.04 (agree), customer assess that screen display of iPhone is more attractive than other brands and has distinctive feature other than that they're interested with the design, it seems futuristic. Moreover, based on customer assessment result, Total average score of Functional benefits is 3.68 (agree), customers has advantages in certain features from the iPhone such as SIRI, iTunes and iCloud that distinguishes it from android, the iPhone is user friendly and also provides applications that can be downloaded through the apple store although this aspect is considered neutral by customers, because Android has more and free purchase applications. The last dimension is the Symbolic benefits which obtained a total average score of 3.79 (agree). The points for this dimension are that the iPhone matches with the customer's life style, not only giving the impression of a more exclusivity than other brands but also better in the eyes of other individuals.

2. Result on Customer commitment is good / Agree category. Based on the Affective aspect, customer assesses that they get a lot of benefits when using the iPhone; they do have a strong attachment and sense of belonging with the iPhone. On the Calculative aspect, they found it difficult to replace the iPhone by moving to another brand of cellphone, because it takes a lot of time and energy.
3. F-test shows result that F_{count} (36.935) is greater than the F_{table} (2.31) which means that H_01 is rejected and H_{a1} is accepted, so it can be concluded that there is simultaneous impact of brand concept dimensions (Aesthetic, Functional and Symbolic benefits) on Customer commitment. As a result of the Coefficient of Determination, it shows that there is a 52.1% impact of Aesthetic, Functional and Symbolic benefits on Customer commitment, the remaining 47.9% is influenced by other variables outside the research regression model.
4. The t test on the research was conducted to analyze partial impact of independent variables on the dependent variable, with the results obtained as follows:

Independent Variables	Value t-count	Value t-table	Research hypothesis	Description
Aesthetic Benefits	2.479	1.984	H_02 declined, H_{a2} accepted	the Aesthetic benefits variable (X1) has a positive and significant impact on the Customer commitment (Y) variable
Functional Benefits	2.230	1.984	H_03 declined, H_{a3} accepted	the Functional benefit variable (X2) has a positive and significant impact on the Customer commitment (Y) variable
Symbolic Benefits	4.120	1.984	H_04 declined, H_{a4} accepted	the Symbolic benefits variable (X3) has a positive and significant impact on the Customer commitment variable (Y).

Based on table t-test above was obtained the regression equation model for this research as follows:

$$Y = 4.229 + 0.577X_1 + 0.706X_2 + 0.955X_3 + \epsilon$$

Based on regression coefficient from the equations, it shows that symbolic benefits have a dominant impact on brand commitment

Suggestion

As for some of the suggestions proposed by the author, among others:

1. Apple Company should maintain the Aesthetic (eg; the catchy feeling customers derive from the attractive display screen), Functional (eg; improving the features of the applications such as the SIRI) and Symbolic (eg; maintaining the exclusive impression among other brands) dimensions that are valued quite well by customers today, but should continue to conduct technological research to get a product that is better than other competitors, as the research shows that Brand Concept dimensions has an impact on Customer commitment both simultaneously and partially.
2. Essentially, Economic (eg; maintaining a quality that constantly matches the exclusive price of the iPhone to give an edge over other brands), Psychology (eg; maintaining that sense of belonging and the feeling of being up to date with modern technology among iPhone Users) and Norms aspects (eg; improving the number of free purchase applications that could be downloaded from the App Store) must be considered in every research conducted by Apple iPhone Company in realizing brand concepts, so that customer commitment is formed.
3. Symbolic benefits are the most influential dimension in shaping Customer Commitment, so Apple iPhone Company should try to continue to maintain that exclusivity both in terms of design and features; so that Apple iPhone users will have their own pride and continue to feel that superiority among their peers and also have that sense of belonging that they will not get from using other smartphone brands.

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